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Modulating the local electron density at built-in interface iron single sites in Fe-CN/MoO₃ heterostructure for enhanced CO₂ reduction to CH₄ and photo-Fenton reaction

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The catalytic efficiency of heterogeneous photocatalytic CO₂ reduction and photo-Fenton H₂O₂ activation is closely related to the local electron density of reaction center atoms. However, electron-hole recombination from random charge transfer significantly restricts the targeted electron delivery to the active center. Herein, Fe-

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Heterostructure
Photocatalysis

C₃N₄/MoO₃ heterojunction with interfacial coordination of atomically dispersed Fe-N₄ sites with the O interface of MoO₃ was synthesized by simple hydrothermal method. Based on the experimental results and density functional theory calculation (DFT), the heterojunction structure fosters accelerated interfacial electron transfer due to directional interfacial electric field (IEF) between Fe-CN and MoO heterogeneous interfaces, and the interfacial bond between Fe-N₄ sites and O at the built-in interface regulates the local electron density of Fe-N₄ active center. DFT further reveals that the interfacial electron flow and concentrated electron density at Fe-N₄ sites result from the coordination between Fe-N₄ and MoO₃ interfaces. This directs electron flow towards the Fe center, significantly enhancing CO₂ adsorption and H₂O₂ conversion efficiency. PDOS analysis shows that the *d*_{yz} and *d*_{z²} orbitals of the isolated Fe atom in Fe-CN overlap with the *p*_z orbital of the O atom in MoO₃, playing a pivotal role in CO₂ adsorption. Consequently, the Fe-CN/MoO₃ heterojunction demonstrated highly efficient photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to CH₄, coupled with benzyl alcohol oxidation and photo-Fenton tetracycline degradation. These findings offer a promising multifunctional catalyst strategy for the development of energy conversion and environmental remediation.

1. Introduction

The excessive burning of fossil fuels caused by the elevated expansion of human activities and industrialization has led to a constant increase in the CO₂ level, posing an alarming threat to sustainable and economic development [1–3]. Fortunately, despite the high stability of CO₂ ($\Delta G^\circ = -394 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$), resulting from C=O dissociation energy (750 kJ mol⁻¹), semiconductor photocatalysts can competently convert CO₂ into useful hydrocarbon fuels using solar light through the “holy grail” reaction [4]. Therefore, artificial photosynthesis, based on photocatalytic CO₂ reduction, is a promising way to address energy diminution and the threats to environmental and global climate issues [5]. Since the pioneering discovery of CO₂ reduction [6], numerous photocatalysts have been investigated for CO₂ reduction [7–11], however, the majority of catalysts still limit their practical application due to their wide band gap, deficient light absorption capacity, stability, etc. [11–14]. On the other hand, the increasing surface and groundwater pollution due to human and clinical activities has attracted considerable attention from the scientific community [15,16]. Particularly, numerous persistent organic pollutants adversely affect aquatic life and human health [17–19]. The designing of novel catalysts to generate reactive oxidation species (ROS), such as hydroxyl radical (•OH) and superoxide radical (•O₂), is crucial for environmental remediation. Fenton reaction on semiconductors has been regarded as a promising technology for reactive •OH radical generation due to its environmentally friendly nature and efficient pollutant removal [20]. Heterogeneous Fenton reaction, the catalytic activation of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) injects electrons to generate •OH radicals via a green and sustainable reaction ($\text{Fe}^{3+} + e^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{2+}; \text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+} + \bullet\text{OH}$) [21]. Therefore, desirable photocatalysts are needed to provide sufficient electrons for the H₂O₂ conversion.

Graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) has been extensively studied in photocatalysis due to its excellent properties, such as low cost and suitable band gap to absorb visible light [22,23]. Particularly, the amorphous/ill-crystallized structure of g-C₃N₄, due to the presence of surface defects and the adjacent polymeric heptazine chain connected with hydrogen bonds, results in immense amino groups, which act as the recombination center and thus consequences in poor photocatalytic performance [24]. Numerous modifications, including band structure tuning [25,26], doping [27,28], heterojunction formation [29,30], etc., have been made to enhance the charge dynamic of g-C₃N₄ during the photocatalytic reaction [31–33]. Recently, atomically dispersed metal-carbon-nitrogen (Fe-C-N) catalysts attracted widespread attention in photocatalysis, particularly in CO₂ reduction and H₂O₂ activation [34–37], due to the presence of active Fe site utilization with high electron density and charge mobility [34]. Importantly, the atomically dispersed Fe single-atom moiety typically enhances the photoexcited electrons on the catalyst surface, resulting in a multi-electron excitation reaction during the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ [38]. Nonetheless, the majority of atomically dispersed Fe single-atom catalysts with limited surface-active sites are not conducive to achieving high catalytic

CO₂ reduction due to high electron-hole pairs recombination resulting from random charge transfer and local electron density at single Fe sites. Therefore, a significant obstacle still stands in the way of the efficient separation and oriented transfer of photogenerated electrons. A significant modification is highly desirable to achieve and regulate the electronic density and charge migration.

Previous studies suggest that the formation of heterojunction structures is an effective way to modulate and tune the local electron density and charge migration. Molybdenum trioxide (MoO₃) has garnered significant attraction in wide-range technological applications due to its structure and shape-dependent characteristics [38–40]. Literature suggests that making a heterojunction structure of MoO₃ with other semiconductors, such as MoS₂, g-C₃N₄, TiO₂, WO₃, Fe₂O₃, and ZnIn₂S₄ can endow potential catalytic activity by enhancing the visible light absorption and regulating charge transfer [40–45]. Therefore, considering the band positions of atomically dispersed Fe-C₃N₄ and MoO₃, a well-established Z-scheme heterojunction can bestow the local electronic density [46–48], charge migration [14,49], and photogenerated charge separation during the photocatalytic reaction for CO₂ reduction and H₂O₂ activation. More importantly, fewer atomically dispersed catalysts have been reported for molecular H₂O₂ activation and/or bifunctional (photodegradation and photoreduction) activities.

Herein, we propose an interfacial Z-scheme heterojunction of atomically dispersed Fe-C₃N₄ and MoO₃ interfaces to modulate the local electron density and orient the charge transfer of the reactive Fe center for promoted CO₂ reduction and H₂O₂ conversion. Experimental and theoretical calculations insight revealed that well-engineered Z-scheme Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction enhanced the local electronic density and charge dynamic at the heterojunction interface. The involvement of the *d* orbital of the isolated Fe atom of Fe-N₄ sites with the non-metal *p* orbital of oxygen orientated the electronic flow through the interface, thereby acting as the electron trap center and directionally driving the photoelectron to accumulate on Fe. With the merits of the Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction, the concentrated electron density at the Fe-N₄ active sites enhanced the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to CH₄ coupled benzyl alcohol oxidation and efficient photo-Fenton oxidation of refractory organic pollutant tetracycline hydrochloride. *In-situ* Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) and free energy calculation unveil that the vital step for CO production is CO₂ hydrogenation towards the formation of *COOH. Simultaneously, the H₂O₂ adsorption energy (*E*_{ads}) of two different H₂O₂ adsorption configurations on Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction explains the most favorable adsorption of H₂O₂ conversion.

2. Experimental

All the chemicals used in this work were of analytical grade, and no further purification was performed before use. Dicyandiamide, iron(III) chloride hexahydrate (FeCl₃·6H₂O), and sodium molybdate (Na₂MoO₄) were purchased from Aladdin Industrial Co., Shanghai. Nitric acid (HNO₃) was obtained from Sinopharm Group Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd. Milli-Q ultrapure deionized water (DI) (>17 mΩ cm) was used as

the reaction solvents.

2.1. Synthesis of C_3N_4 (CN)

Polymeric carbon nitride ($g-C_3N_4$) was prepared by dissolving 2 g of dicyandiamide in 40 mL deionized water (DI) and sonicated until complete dispersion. The suspension was kept on stirring in an oil bath at 80 °C until the water evaporated. The white precipitate was dried in a vacuum oven overnight. Finally, the obtained dicyandiamide was fine ground and heated at 550 °C for 4 h in an argon atmosphere (5 °C/min). The resultant product was denoted as CN.

2.2. Synthesis of atomically dispersed Fe-CN

In a typical synthesis of atomically dispersed Fe- C_3N_4 with nitrogen vacancies, 2 g of dicyandiamide in 40 mL DI water was thoroughly dispersed by sonication. Then, a certain amount of $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ was added into the suspension and kept on continuous stirring at 80 °C until the whole water evaporated. The resultant mixture was again dried in a vacuum oven overnight and finally ground into fine powder. The product was calcined at 550 °C in an argon atmosphere for 4 h (5 °C/min) and then ground to fine powder. To engineer N vacancies and atomically dispersed Fe-N sites, the powder was recalcined at 620 °C for 4 h. The obtained product was named 0.1-Fe-CN, 0.2-Fe-CN, and 0.25-Fe-CN, based on the wt.% of Fe.

2.3. Synthesis of Fe- C_3N_4 /MoO₃ heterojunction (Fe-CN/MoO)

The 0.2-Fe-CN was chosen as a standard sample for the construction of interface Fe- C_3N_4 /MoO₃ heterojunction structure (Fe-CN/MoO) based on the optimal mass fraction and catalytic activity. The mass fraction of Fe in 0.2-Fe-CN determined by ICP-MS is 1.05 wt%. Briefly, 5 mM Na_2MoO_4 was ultrasonically dispersed in 60 mL of 0.4 M HNO_3 solution in water and adjusted the pH = ~ 2. Then, a certain amount of Fe-CN (0.2-Fe-CN) was added to the above solution and ultrasonicated for 10 min. The suspension was further kept on stirring at room temperature for another 1.5 h until the mixture was evenly dispersed. The mixture solution was then transferred into a Teflon-line stainless steel autoclave and subsequently heated at 180 °C for 12 h. The final product was obtained after washing and drying in a vacuum oven for 24 h at 60 °C. Pristine MoO₃ nanowires were obtained using the same procedure without adding Fe-CN. The final catalysts were named MoO₃ (MoO), Fe-CN/1-MoO, Fe-CN/3-MoO, Fe-CN/5-MoO, and Fe-CN/7-MoO, based on the amount of Fe-CN. Explanation about the sample characterization, photocatalytic activity, *in situ* diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS), and density functional theory (DFT) computational methodology are mentioned in the [supporting information data](#).

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the formation of atomically dispersed Fe-CN and interface Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction, (b) XRD patterns, and (c) FTIR spectra of CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/MoO catalysts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure characterization and chemical state analysis

The synthesis of iron single-atom carbon nitride (Fe-CN) and Fe-CN/MoO₃ heterojunction is illustrated in Fig. 1a. Initially, we synthesized a series of Fe single-atom Fe-CN catalysts by calcinating FeCl₃·6H₂O and dicyandiamide at 550 °C in different mass percentages of iron salt (0.5, 2.0, and 2.5 mass percent of FeCl₃·6H₂O). For further crystallization, engineering vacancies, and anchoring the Fe single atom, the synthesized catalysts were further calcined at 620 °C in argon atmosphere, resulting in the formation of crystalline atomically dispersed Fe single atom anchored Fe-CN. The obtained catalysts were tested for CO₂ reduction to CH₄ coupled with benzyl alcohol oxidation and photo-Fenton of tetracycline hydrochloride oxidation. The optimal wt.% Fe single-atom 0.2-Fe-CN sample was taken as the representative sample for heterojunction formation. The well-established interface heterojunction of Fe-CN nanosheets and MoO₃ nanowires was carried out by simple hydrothermal method in highly acidic conditions (pH = 2). After the addition of Fe-CN and stirring for 1.5 h in highly acidic medium facilitates the surface roughness of Fe-CN and the well-crystallization of MoO₃ nanowires, consequences in intimate heterojunction interfaces between Fe-CN and MoO₃.

Fig. S1 shows the XRD patterns of pristine g-C₃N₄ (CN), atomically dispersed 0.2-Fe-CN and 0.25-Fe-CN. A slight decrease and peak shifting of the corresponding (002) peak from 27.49° for CN to 27.52° and 27.61° for Fe-CN of the heptazine network is detected for Fe-CN samples compared to intrinsic CN (the inset Fig. S1) [50,51]. Relative to CN, the intensity of Fe-CN interfacial stacking of the conjugated construction peak (001) at 2θ = 13.0° decreased or almost disappeared in 0.25-Fe-CN, which is caused by the interaction between the Fe atom and the

heptazine unit, confirming the successful coordination of the Fe atoms with neighboring N atoms [50]. Similarly, relative to the pristine CN, Fe-CN, and MoO₃, the XRD patterns of Fe-CN/MoO₃ heterojunction catalysts comprises the characteristic diffraction peaks at 2θ = 12.83°, 23.39°, 25.77°, 27.37°, 33.77°, and 39.05°, which can be indexed to the (020), (110), (040), (021), (111), (060), of the crystal planes of α-MoO₃ and h-MoO₃ [JCPDS No. 35–0609, 21–0569] (Fig. 1b). After Fe-CN (nanosheet)MoO₃(nanowires) heterojunction formation, additional peaks at 2θ = 19.33°, and 49.3° in the XRD pattern, which can be indexed to (200) and (008) planes of h-MoO₃ [JCPDS No. 21–0569] [52]. Interestingly, the intensity of the diffraction peak of (021) largely shifted to the (040) peak after heterojunction formation, which is due to the bond formation between the Fe atoms of the Fe-CN (Fe-N₄ moieties) interface with the oxygen interface of MoO₃, resulting in vacancy formation [53]. Besides, the polarity interaction between the surface oxygen atom and the carbon atom may cause the phase transition of MoO₃. The same changes were observed in the s-triazine peak in the infrared spectra (FTIR) spectra of the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction (Fig. 1c). The FTIR spectra of CN and Fe-CN show the evident formation of the C=N-C and C-N-C network of the basic C-N heterocycle stretching and the breathing modes of the tri-s-triazine unit in the range of 1100–1600 cm⁻¹ and 810 cm⁻¹, respectively. Moreover, the FTIR spectra of MoO₃ show the characteristic stretching vibration of the Mo=O bond at 968 cm⁻¹ and the Mo-O bond at 854 and 558 cm⁻¹ [52,54]. In accordance with the XRD results, after the interfacial bond formation between Fe-CN and MoO₃, the intensity of the corresponding C-N-C network of the basic C-N heterocycle stretching decreased while the peak width of M=O at 968 cm⁻¹ increases, showing the coordination of Fe with the surface O of MoO₃ interface [45,50,53]. No additional XRD diffraction or IR absorption that corresponds to any other organic species is detected, confirming the successful formation of the heterojunction

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a, b) MoO₃, (c, d) Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction, (e, f) TEM images of Fe-CN, (g, h) HRTEM and HAADF-STEM images of Fe-CN, (i, j) TEM image of Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction, (k, l) HRTEM images of Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction.

structure.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of pristine MoO_3 show smooth-surfaced nanowires without prominent aggregates (Fig. 2a, b), and the transmission electron microscope (TEM) images exhibit the width of the nanowires is ~ 150 – 180 nm, and a few microns in length, respectively (Fig. S2a, b). The crystal structure of α - MoO_3 is extremely anisotropic, with two distorted planes of $[\text{MoO}_6]$ octahedra forming a bilayer by sharing octahedral edges in $[001]$ direction, and the bilayers stack up along the $[010]$ direction due to weak van der Waals forces. Therefore, the α - MoO_3 crystals preferentially grow in the $[001]$ direction [52,55,56], forming belt-like structures with exposed (010) facets (Fig. S2c, d) [54,57,58]. According to the SEM images (Fig. 1c, d), the MoO_3 nanowires are confined in ultrathin Fe-CN nanosheets. Similarly, the TEM images of Fe-CN (Fig. 2e, f) exhibit highly mesoporous nanosheet morphology with consecutive several microns thin flakes and embedded wrinkles in the structure. The mesoporous wrinkled structure mainly originated from the co-polymerization of the Fe-CN structure in controlled heat etching. The HRTEM image of Fe-CN (Fig. 2g) shows two distinct sets of lattice fringes (0.332 nm and 0.326 nm), corresponding to the (002) crystal plane of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, associated with the periodic stacking of layers in graphitic carbon nitride ($g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$) [50,59]. However, the lattice fringes of 0.332 nm are quite approximated to the interlayer spacing of graphite structure (≈ 0.335 nm, Fe- N_4 single atomic site) [51,60], consistent with the XRD shifting of the (002) peak, and indicates the increased stacking distance. High-angle annular dark field scanning electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) further examines the atomic level Fe-site in Fe-CN (Fig. 2h) (atomically dispersed Fe atoms in Fe-CN, the region tagged in white). Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) mapping of the HAADF-STEM image of Fe-CN confirms the uniform distribution of the atomically dispersed Fe atom and C and N elements (Fig. S3). The EDS mapping images of Fe-CN show

comparatively fewer N contents due to the co-polymerization of Fe-CN, indicating the N vacancies in the Fe-CN structure. To confirm the heterojunction interfaces between Fe-CN and MoO_3 , the TEM images exhibit Fe-CN confined MoO_3 nanowires structure (Fig. 2i, j). HRTEM images (Fig. 2k) show distinct layers of the close interface structure MoO_3 nanowire and Fe-CN-nanosheet. The lattice fringes of 0.38 nm and 0.332 nm (Fig. 2l) can be ascribed to the (110) and (002) planes of MoO_3 , the stacking layer of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$, and interlayer spacing of graphite structure. Moreover, the corresponding HAADF-STEM EDS mapping images (Fig. S4) show the uniform distribution of C, N, Fe, O, and Mo elements, confirming the successful heterojunction formation with multi-intimate interfaces.

The photocatalytic reaction highly depends on the surface area and the number of active sites on the surface of the catalyst. The N_2 adsorption rate of Fe-CN is higher in the low-pressure region compared to CN, and the Fe-CN/3-MoO is the highest, confirming numerous micropores and mesopores (< 2 nm and > 10 nm) (Fig. S5a), where the majority of pore size distribution is located between 1.5 to 4.5 nm. However, in Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction, the pore volume of micropores slightly decreases, and the density of mesopores increases significantly compared to CN and Fe-CN (Fig. S5b). Notably, the BET surface area analysis and the pore size distribution show that the heterojunction formation helps to increase the surface area and porosity, consequently contributing to high surface-active sites and enhanced catalytic activity (Table S1). Thus, the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction with numerous micro-mesopores can provide a large surface area for CO_2 adsorption and can effectively accelerate the mass transfer and promote the reaction of the inner active sites.

X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy (XAFS) is used to investigate the chemical state and coordination environment of Fe single atom site in Fe-CN. The ICP-MS analysis indicates the Fe contents in 0.2-

Fig. 3. (a) Fe K-edge XANES spectra of Fe-CN, standard Fe foil, Fe_2O_3 , and Fe_3O_4 , (b) Fourier-transformed (FT) curves at R space, and (c) The corresponding EXAFS R space fitting result for Fe-CN; XPS high-resolution orbit scan spectra (d) survey spectra of CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO, (e) C 1 s, (f) N 1 s, (g) Fe 2p, (h) Mo 3d, and (i) O 1 s.

Fe-CN is about 1.05 % (Table S2). The Fe K-edge XANES spectra of Fe-CN show that the absorption edge position of Fe-CN is lower than Fe₂O₃ and Fe₃O₄ and higher than Fe-foil, indicating the valence state of Fe is located between +2 and +3 (Fig. 3a). Moreover, the shifting of the absorption edge toward the lower energy of Fe-CN (inset Fig. 3a) suggests a high electron density of the Fe site (Fe-N₄ moieties) [61], which might be due to the introduction of nitrogen vacancies during the copolymerization of the as-obtained Fe-CN. Similarly, more detailed information around the Fe single-atom site in Fe-CN compared to Fe-foil, Fe₂O₃, and Fe₃O₄ was further investigated by Fourier-transformed extended Fe K-edge EXAFS (Fig. 3b, S6). In the *k*³-weighted *k*-space spectra of Fe-CN, the main peak displays around 1.5 Å, corresponding to the Fe-N bond [62], and no peak for Fe-Fe at 2.2 Å is detected, indicating the atomically dispersed Fe site is in Fe-CN. According to the FT-EXAFS fitted curves in the R space of Fe-CN (Fig. 3c, S7, Table S3), the coordination number obtained for the Fe-N site is 4, which strongly suggests that the atomic Fe-N₄ center is introduced in the Fe single atom g-C₃N₄ structure.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is used to further elucidate the chemical valence state of atomically dispersed Fe in the Fe-CN and the effect on the chemical environment of the Fe site after the interface Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction formation. The survey XPS spectrum of pristine CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/MoO confirms the presence of Fe, C, N, O, and Mo elements in these samples (Fig. 3d), and the atomic ratio of the elements obtained from XPS is shown in Table S4. In the C 1s XPS spectra of CN and Fe-CN (Fig. 3e), the peak at 284.7 eV can be assigned to the adventitious carbon species of the graphite *sp*² hybridized C=C bond [63], while the N-C=N *sp*² C peak at 288.1 eV accounts for the majority in pristine CN and Fe-CN. Besides the peak broadening, caused by the local Fe site in the graphitic ring, no obvious peak shifting is detected. However, in the C1 spectra of Fe-CN/3-MoO, in contrast to CN and Fe-CN, an overwhelming increase in the *sp*² C=C peak is detected, which is caused by the unavoidable graphitic carbon bond of the CN with the surface oxygen of MoO interface. The newly originated peak at 286.1 eV in the C 1s spectra further corroborates the formation of the C=O coordination, suggesting intimate interface contact in Fe-CN/3-MoO [51,63]. The N 1s spectra of pristine CN, Fe-CN, and Fe-CN/MoO show characteristic peaks at 398.43, 399.72, and 400.8 eV for C=N=C, N-(C)₃, and C-N-H, respectively (Fig. 3f). Compared to CN, a peak shift of ~ 0.25 eV towards higher binding energy is observed, which is caused by anchoring a single atom Fe site in Fe-CN and the formation of N vacancies by co-polymerization of Fe-CN. In the case of Fe-CN/3-MoO, a slight shift towards the lower binding energy by ~ 0.14 eV is detected, due to the coordination of the Fe single atom site with the surface O of the MoO interface. The same phenomenon was observed in the XPS spectra of Fe 2p of Fe-CN and Fe-CN/3-MoO (Fig. 3g), indicating the redistribution of electron density between the surface oxygen to the adjacent isolated Fe-N₄ sites in a π -conjugated delocalized CN network (delocalization of Fe 3*d* and O 2*p* orbitals), resulting in high concentrated electron density at Fe-N₄ interface of Fe-CN. The results can be further explained in detail by DFT calculations. The Mo 3*d* spectra of pristine MoO and Fe-CN/3MoO show the characteristic peaks at 232.8 and 236 eV, which can be assigned to the Mo⁶⁺ oxidation state of Mo (Fig. 3h). A slight shift towards higher binding energy in the Mo 3*d* peak could be assigned to the coordination attachment of the surface O at the MoO₃ interface with the Fe-CN interface. The O 1s spectra of pristine MoO show the characteristic lattice oxygen peak at 530.7 eV, while the O 1s of Fe-CN/3MoO account for a higher concentration of surface oxygen vacancies (O_v) peak at 530.89 eV (Fig. 3i). The shifting of the O 1s peak towards lower binding energy and higher concentration of the surface O_v peak indicates that the heterojunction formation introduces abundant surface oxygen vacancies when the two interfaces are in intimate contact, which was further confirmed by EPR spectra (Fig. S8). The XPS results show that the coordination environment of the local Fe site and the surface O at the MoO interface highly changed, confirming the successful formation of the heterojunction interface Fe-CN/MoO.

3.2. Band structure and interfacial carrier dynamic analysis

In a realistic view, potentially efficient photocatalysts must meet the requirements, such as strong visible light absorption, excellent photo-corrosion stability, and the separation of the photogenerated charge carriers to meet the desirable catalytic activity. The optical properties analysis was disclosed in detail to explore the effect of isolated Fe single-atom sites and the interface heterojunction structure formation. The UV-vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) spectra show the impact of visible light absorption of isolated Fe single-atom Fe-N₄ sites and the formation of the interface heterojunction structure, displaying an obvious red shift in the intrinsic absorption edges of Fe-CN (469 nm) compared to pristine CN (448 nm) and MoO (409 nm), respectively (Fig. 4a). On the other hand, Fe-CN/3-MoO (515 nm) shows a prominent red shift in the absorption edge, indicating a strong visible light absorption capacity of the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction. The bandgap calculated from the Tauc plots (Fig. 4b), using the Kubelka-Munk function, are 2.85, 2.70, 3.30, and 2.79 eV, respectively. In contrast to CN, the decrease in the bandgap of Fe-CN is due to the formation of defect states and the introduction of new Fe energy levels below the Fermi level. Likewise, after the heterojunction formation, the bandgap of Fe-CN/3-MoO decreases due to the coordination of O interface of MoO with the Fe of FeN₄ moieties and the adventitious carbon species of graphite *sp*² hybridized C-C linkage of the Fe-CN interface. Notably, the formation of intimate heterojunction interfaces between Fe-CN and MoO possibly connects by multiple coordination between the two surfaces, thus generating surface defects and ultimately enhancing the visible light absorption capacity. The valence band XPS (VB-XPS) spectra show that the valence band edge (VB) of CN shifted from 2.06 eV to 1.89 eV after the atomically dispersed Fe site (Fig. 4c, d). Similarly, the VB of MoO is shifted from 3.55 to 3.36 eV due to surface defects level above the VB. Based on Fig. 4c, d, the conduction band edges (CB) are calculated as -0.79, -0.81, and 0.58 eV for CN, Fe-CN, and MoO, respectively. According to the standard potential of CO₂ reduction to various hydrocarbons and O₂/O₂⁻, the CB position of Fe-CN in Fe-CN/3-MoO perfectly lies above standard potentials, which is highly conducive to enhanced charge transfer and suppressed electron-hole recombination via the Z-scheme photocatalytic charge transfer.

The photogenerated carriers' dynamic is studied by fluorescence (PL) measurement. Pristine CN and MoO show intensive PL emission at ~ 466 and ~ 469 nm due to the sub-band transition and the intrinsic bandgap emission, respectively (Fig. S9). Similarly, atomically dispersed Fe-CN shows lower PL emission intensity compared to bulk CN, while the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction exhibits much lower PL emission due to highly suppressed radiative charge recombination caused by the introduction of Fe energy level and the defects level after the heterojunction formation, reflecting the low probability of band-to-band electron-hole recombination. Moreover, the smaller arc radius of Fe-CN and Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction in the Nyquist plots (in dark and under visible light irradiation) further supports the fast charge transfer and highly suppressed recombination of electron holes (Fig. S10). Time-resolved photoluminescence (TR-PL) curves of the average lifetime and the corresponding carrier dynamics are shown in Fig. 4e, Table S5. Pristine CN (τ_{av} = 4.87 ns) shows the shortest average lifetime, in contrast to Fe-CN (τ_{av} = 4.15 ns), while the heterojunction Fe-CN/3-MoO prolonged fluorescence average lifetime (τ_{av} = 3.5 ns). The transient photocurrent spectra (Fig. 4f) show a slightly higher initial current density of MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO shows the highest and most stable current density, suggesting improved charge transfer and effectively inhibited band-to-band charge recombination. Based on the above results, it can be concluded that the formation of the heterojunction structure could deviate the interfacial charge transfer via the directional interfacial electric field charge transfer mechanism, thus effectively enhancing the charge dynamic of the photogenerated charge species.

Fig. 4. Optical properties analysis of (a, b) UV/Vis diffuse reflectance spectra and Tauc plots of different samples, (c) VB-XPS spectra of CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO, (d) The electronic band structure and the calculated CB and VB potentials of CN, Fe-CN, and MoO, (e) Time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) emission spectra, and (f) transient photocurrent responses spectra of CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO.

3.3. Electronic structure and the mechanism of boosted charge dynamic

The optimized electronic structures of Fe-CN and MoO crystal by density functional theory (DFT) calculations are shown in Figs. S11 and S12. The optimized Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction interface structure shows that Fe in the Fe-CN forms an interfacial coordination with the O atom interface of the MoO surface, which acts as an electron bridge for spatial carrier separation and electron transfer channel between the two interfaces [(Fig. 5a(i, ii), b(i, ii))]. The bond formation of Fe with N of Fe-CN (Fe-N₄ moieties) and O of MoO (Fe-O) was confirmed by electron density difference (EDD, rotated around different axes). The EDD map results show the net charge depletion on the central Fe atom (the blue color indicates the charge depletion) and charge accumulation on N and O (the yellow color shows the charge accumulation) due to the electronegativity difference between Fe, N, and O, therefore determining the electron flow at the heterojunction interface [(Fig. 5a(i, ii), b(i, ii))]. The Bader charge analysis shows that the positive charge density on the Fe of Fe-CN increases from 0.78 to 0.97 eV after heterojunction formation [64], suggesting strong coordination of the Fe-N₄ sites with the O atom on the MoO surface (Fig. S13). After heterojunction formation, the d-band center of Fe was shifted downwards the Fermi level from 0.341 eV to -0.510 eV (Fig. S14) [53]. Similarly, the total density of state (TDOS) spectra of Fe-CN show that the electrons in both channels are in identical states (Fig. S15). After heterojunction formation, the TDOS spectra of Fe show a dramatic change in the down channel spectra and a shift below the Fermi level, which indicates that the Fe electron is directed toward the O atom (Fig. S16). The specific orbital overlapping of Fe and O orbitals (Fe *d*-orbitals and O *p*-orbitals) in interface Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction was studied by the partial density of state (PDOS). The PDOS spectra show exciting interaction of Fe *d*_{yz} and *d*_{z²} orbitals of Fe-CN overlap with the O *p*_z orbital of MoO at Fe-/CN/MoO interface, while the rest of Fe *d*-orbitals do not hybridize with any of the O *p*-orbitals (Fig. 5c, S17) [65]. The directional interfacial electric field (IEF) between Fe-CN and MoO heterogeneous interfaces was substantiated by calculating the work function (ϕ) (Fig. 5d, e). The estimated ϕ value for Fe-CN(002) ($\phi = 5.22$ eV) is smaller than the MoO(110) ($\phi = 8.02$ eV) interface, indicating electrons flow from Fe-CN to the MoO until

reaching the same E_F at the built-in interface. Such a spontaneous electron transfer between the two interfaces constructs the IEF. During visible light irradiation, the IEF, in combination with the bend bending, accelerates the CB electron of the MoO and the VB hole of Fe-CN, to their interface, thus suppressing the recombination of photogenerated charge species. Consequently, the electron retains in the CN of Fe-CN and the hole in the VB of MoO, therefore harnessing the CO₂ reduction and the photo Fenton reaction (Fig. 5f).

3.4. Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction coupled with benzyl alcohol oxidation

The photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to CO and CH₄ coupled with benzyl alcohol oxidation of catalysts was studied in CO₂/H₂O mixture without any sacrificial agent. The main products detected under visible light CO₂ reduction are CO, CH₄, and benzaldehyde, with CH₄ being the dominant for Fe-CN/MoO. Initially, the CO₂ reduction activity of various Fe-CN_x catalysts was tested (Fig. 6a, S18), where 0.2-Fe-CN was chosen as the optimal Fe content for atomically dispersed Fe-CN, which achieved the highest yield of CO (4.76 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), CH₄ (2.49 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), and benzaldehyde (1.053 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$). The lower CO₂ reduction efficiency of low Fe loading content in atomically dispersed Fe-CN (0.1-Fe-CN) can be attributed to deficient Fe-N₄ sites (Fig. S18a-c). However, the higher Fe content (0.25-Fe-CN) could lead to the aggregation of Fe and the reduction of Fe-N₄ active sites, which hinders the catalytic activity of Fe-CN. Similarly, among the various heterojunction catalysts, Fe-CN/3-MoO achieved the best CO₂ reduction to CH₄ and benzaldehyde with 6.16 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$ and 2.19 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively (Fig. S19a-d). At first, with the lower Fe-CN concentration, the catalytic activity of Fe-CN/1-MoO to CH₄ and benzaldehyde (2.087 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, 0.81 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) is almost similar to 0.2-Fe-CN. However, by increasing the Fe-CN content (Fe-CN/3-MoO), a notable increase in CO₂ conversion was achieved, indicating the optimal concentration of the two components (Fe-CN and MoO₃) built-in interface heterostructure. The decline in CO₂ reduction activity of Fe-CN/5-MoO and Fe-CN/7-MoO can be ascribed to the excessive deposition of Fe-CN on the surface of MoO₃ nanowires, resulting in the formation of a dense structure, which interrupts the electronic flow at the interface and consequently reduces

Fig. 5. Theoretical DFT calculation analysis, [(a) (i, ii), b(i, ii)] Electron density difference (EDD) between Fe and N, and Fe and O in at the Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction interfaces (the blue color indicates the charge depletion and the yellow shows the charge accumulation, the red and pink colors represent O and Mo atoms, the gray, blue, yellow, colors represents C, N, and Fe atoms), (c) Partial density of state (PDOS) between Fe (d_{yz} , d_{xz}) and O (p_y , p_x , p_z) orbitals, (d, e) Calculated average potential profile along z-direction of Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction, and (f) Schematic of the formation of Z-scheme heterojunction of Fe-CN(002) and MoO(110) interfaces and the proposed charge transfer and separation mechanism. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

the catalytic activity due to high electron/hole recombination. Notably, no CO_2 photoreduction over pristine MoO_3 was detected due to its positive CB potential. However, the heterojunction structure Fe-CN/3-MoO, in contrast to CN and Fe-CN, shows the highest products yields of CO ($14.02 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, $3.50 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), CH_4 ($24.64 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, $6.16 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) and benzaldehyde ($8.78 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$, $2.19 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), outperforms the CN ($\text{CO} = 1.30 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $\text{CH}_4 = 1.52 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, benzaldehyde = $0.63 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), Fe-CN ($\text{CO} = 2.49 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, $\text{CH}_4 = 4.76 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$, benzaldehyde = $1.053 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$), MoO and most previously reported g- C_3N_4 -based catalysts (Fig. 6b-e, Table S6a, b). The photostability is an essential factor in heterojunction catalysis. The cyclic CO_2 reduction reaction of Fe-CN/3-MoO was tested for three recycle reactions, showing no prominent decline in the catalytic activity, indicating its high photostability (Fig. 6f). Notably, the CO_2 reduction

over Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction suggests the directional interfacial electric field charge transfer at the two interfaces; otherwise, in the case of conventional Type-II heterojunction, there will be no CO_2 reduction. The highest CO_2 reduction activity of Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction can be attributed to the enhanced charge dynamic and boosted charge transfer between Fe-CN and MoO_3 interfaces. Similarly, not only is the boosted directional charge transfer solely responsible for the enhanced catalytic activity, but the atomically dispersed Fe-N₄ center facilitates the charge modulation and acts as an active site for CO_2 adsorption.

The conversion of CO_2 involves the adsorption of CO_2 molecules on the surface of catalysts, which is particularly difficult due to the stable close shell electronic configuration of CO_2 . Considering the adsorption of CO_2 and the generation of reactive active species like $\text{CO}_2^{\cdot -}$, HCO_3^- , $\text{CO}_3^{\cdot -}$, etc., which is aimed to activate the C—O bond and then convert to

Fig. 6. Photocatalytic activity of $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixture (a) Yield of products ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) of CO_2 reduction to CO, CH_4 , benzaldehyde over 0.1-Fe-CN, 0.2-Fe-CN, and 0.25-Fe-CN, (b, c, d) Yield of products ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$) CO, CH_4 , and benzaldehyde over CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO, (e) Yield of products ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) over CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO, and (f) Recycled reactions yield of products ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}\text{h}^{-1}$) over Fe-CN/3-MoO (three repeated experiments to estimate the error bar).

the desirable products, the *in situ* diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) was performed during the $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption and activation process on the surface of catalysts. The adsorption of the $\text{CO}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ mixture over Fe-CN/3-MoO shows various peaks of the characteristic carbonate species during CO_2 adsorption (Fig. 7a, S20). Fe-CN and Fe-CN/3-MoO show comparable CO_2 adsorption peaks, indicating that the main CO_2 conversion takes place by the CB electrons of the Fe-CN interface, where the atomically dispersed Fe- N_4 sites facilitate the adsorption of CO_2 molecules. The DRIFTS spectra (Fig. 7a, b) show characteristic adsorption peaks at 1040, 1146, 1309, 1369, and 1509 cm^{-1} for monodentate carbonate (m-CO_3^{2-}), 1569 cm^{-1} for bidentate carbonate (b-CO_3^{2-}), 1200, and 1458 cm^{-1} for bicarbonate (HCO_3^-), indicating the adsorption and activation of CO_2 molecule on the surface of catalysts. However, the adsorption characteristic of Fe-CN/MoO is higher compared to Fe-CN, suggesting high product yield. The adsorption band at 1634 cm^{-1} assigned to COOH^- originated when the adsorbed CO_2 combines with H^+ and is partly converted into COOH^* [66]. The prolonged irradiation shows a gradual conversion of CO_2 reduction to CO, CH_4 , and benzaldehyde (Fig. 7b). Additionally, the band of asymmetric stretching vibration of adsorbed benzyl alcohol is detected at 3050 cm^{-1} (Fig. 7a), indicating the unassociated aromatic ring absorption band around $2960\text{--}3030\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The characteristic band around $2590\text{--}2760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the vibration mode of $\delta(\text{CHO}^*)$, indicating the newly generated benzaldehyde, thus confirming the simultaneous CO_2 reduction and the benzyl alcohol oxidation. Notably, the increase in the surface density of CO_2 conversion with irradiation time suggests the effective interaction of the electrons on the catalyst's surface and the CO_2 molecule. The possible conversion of CO_2 reduction and simultaneous benzyl alcohol oxidation pathways can be formulated according to the following reaction:

Essential considerations of the CO_2 reduction to CH_4 process and the

CO_2 adsorption on the surface of Fe-CN and Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction were evaluated by free energy profiles with the lowest energy path. The optimized energy of all possible CO_2 intermediates is given in Table S7. According to the calculated results (Fig. 7c, d, Fig. S21, S22, and Table S8,9), the CO_2 molecules were first adsorbed on Fe-CN and Fe-CN/MoO surface and coupled with proton/electron and converted $^*\text{COOH}$. The free energy change of CO_2 hydrogenation on the surface of Fe-CN is -0.35 eV , while the Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction is -0.81 eV , indicating a higher rate of CO_2 hydrogenation on the surface of Fe-CN/MoO compared to Fe-CN. Notably, the main step for CO production is CO_2 hydrogenation towards the formation of $^*\text{COOH}$ and the free energy change during CO_2 conversion [67]. After that, $^*\text{COOH}$ will pair with a proton/electron and produce CO and H_2O molecules. The change of Gibbs energy of Fe-CN and Fe-CN/MoO with CO molecule is -0.85 eV and -0.67 eV , respectively, indicating highly promoted CO hydrogenation on the Fe-CN/MoO interface. The formation energy of $^*\text{CHO}$ on the Fe-CN surface (-0.96 eV) is higher than that of CO, while the Fe-CN/MoO surface is much lower than CO, suggesting much easier CO_2 reduction to CH_4 [66,68]. In conclusion, according to PDOS calculation of Fe-CN/MoO and free energy results, the rate of CO_2 reduction greatly depends on the availability of d_{yz} and d_z^2 orbital. As the availability of d_{yz} and d_z^2 orbital increases, the rate of CO_2 reduction reaction decreases. Furthermore, according to the Bader charge and d-band center, the electron-donating species decrease the rate of CO_2 reduction, while the electron-withdrawing agent increases the rate of the CO_2 reduction reaction.

3.5. Analysis of photo-Fenton reaction mechanism

Additionally, the Fenton-like photocatalytic activity of the synthesized catalysts was investigated for tetracycline hydrochloride (TCH) oxidation under visible-light irradiation ($\lambda \geq 420\text{ nm}$). The adsorption and oxidation of TCH in the presence of H_2O_2 and visible light/ H_2O_2 without catalysts is negligible (Fig. 8a), and the Fe-CN/3-MoO without H_2O_2 cannot efficiently activate H_2O_2 to degrade TCH ($\sim 70\%$ in 80 min). However, the addition of H_2O_2 (Fe-CN/3-MoO/ H_2O_2 /Vis) highly boosted the TCH oxidation to $\sim 98\%$ (Fig. 8a, Fig. S23), indicating the Fenton oxidation of TCH. The addition of H_2O_2 generates a high number

Fig. 7. *In situ* diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectra (DRIFTS) of CO₂ adsorption intermediates (a) Adsorption in the dark in CO₂/H₂O mixture over Fe-CN and Fe-CN/3-MoO, (b) Under visible light irradiation in CO₂/H₂O mixture over Fe-CN/3-MoO; (c, d) Free energy diagrams of CO₂ adsorption and conversion to CH₄ for Fe-CN and Fe-CN/3-MoO.

of reactive oxidation species, consequently enhancing the oxidation activity of TCH. The Fenton oxidation of TCH of different catalysts (CN, Fe-CN, MoO, Fe-CN/MoO in H₂O₂/Vis light) (Fig. 8b) shows that CN can degrade about ~ 62 % of TCH. In contrast, the degradation of TCH over Fe-CN highly increases (~ 71 %) due to the presence of isolated Fe atom in Fe-CN, which acts as the activation site for H₂O₂. The degradation of TCH over Fe-CN/MoO is not only boosted by the atomically dispersed Fe-N₄ sites but also due to the effective Z-scheme charge transfer and high separation efficiency of photogenerated charge carriers at the Fe-CN and MoO interfaces, showing comparable or outperformed efficiency than most previously reported g-C₃N₄-based catalysts (Table S10a, b). Fig. 8c compares the TCH degradation over various Fe-CN/MoO/H₂O₂/Vis systems. Initially, the degradation efficiency of Fe-CN/1-MoO (~76 %) was not as high, but increasing the content of Fe-CN and MoO to obtain optimal content of the two components achieving the highest degradation of Fe-CN/3-MoO (~ 98 %), while

further increasing the contents decreases efficiency (Fe-CN/5-MoO= ~ 92 %, Fe-CN/7-MoO= ~ 9 %). The high content of Fe-CN nanosheet on the surface of MoO nanowires hinders the catalyst's active sites and the penetration of the visible light to the surface of catalysts, thus decreasing the degradation efficiency. The reaction kinetic [pseudo-first-order kinetic constant (k)] (Fig. S24) shows a notable k/min of 0.029 min⁻¹ for Fe-CN/3-MoO, nearly 3, 2.1, and 4.2 times higher than CN, Fe-CN, and MoO. Additionally, the degradation pathway of TCH degradation was studied by the HPLC-MS method at different irradiation times, and the results of the TCH oxidation intermediates were derived based on the HPLC-MS method (Fig. S25, S26). The discussion regarding the HPLC-MS analysis of the TCH photodegradation intermediates is provided in the supporting information Section 4.

The stability of photocatalysts is a crucial factor in practical catalytic application. In order to investigate the crystal structure and morphological stability of the as-synthesized Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction, the

Fig. 8. (a) Degradation curves of TCH degradation in sole photocatalytic process, Fenton reaction, and photocatalytic activation H_2O_2 process with or without Fe-CN/3-MoO, (b) TCH degradation curves over CN, Fe-CN, MoO, and Fe-CN/3-MoO catalysts during photocatalytic H_2O_2 activation, (c) TCH degradation curves of different Fe-CN/MoO catalysts (three repeated experiments to estimate the error bar); ESR spectra of radical adducts (d) DMPO-superoxide radical ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$), (e) hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$), and (f) TEMP-singlet oxygen $^1\text{O}_2$ in dark and under visible light with and without H_2O_2 (reaction conditions: TC = 10 mg/L, catalyst dosage = 0.5 g/L, H_2O_2 concentration = 1 mM, pH = 6.5).

photodegradation reaction of TCH was systematically recycled from 3 consecutive cycle experiments. No apparent decline in the degradation performance is observed (Fig. S27). Additionally, the XRD patterns and the SEM images of the fresh and used Fe-CN/3-MoO sample after three successive degradation experiments show no crystal structure deformation (Fig. S28a–c). The TEM and HRTEM images of the used Fe-CN/3-MoO sample further confirm the high stability of the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction catalyst (Figs. S28d–f).

Scavengers, such as ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA-2Na, hole/ h^+), *tert*-butanol (TBA, hydroxyl radical/ $\cdot\text{OH}$), hexachloroethane (superoxide radical/ $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$), and furfuryl alcohol (FFA, singlet oxygen/ $^1\text{O}_2$) and EPR tests were investigated in detail to explore the oxidation mechanism of TCH over Fe-CN/MoO/ H_2O_2 /scavenger system and the involvement of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the Fenton reaction. When the TBA, hexachloroethane, and FFA were introduced into the reaction system (Fig. S29), the $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, and $^1\text{O}_2$ were specifically inhibited, indicating their significant role in the photoreaction. However, adding EDTA-2Na has no specific effect, showing that the h^+ plays a minor role during TCH degradation. FFA, as a scavenger of non-radical reactive oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) in the Fe-CN/MoO/ H_2O_2 /FFA system, indicates that the degradation of TC was highly inhibited in the presence of FFA, suggesting that the dissolved oxygen in water can facilitate the formation of $^1\text{O}_2$. Similarly, the $^1\text{O}_2$ capture experiment in N_2 atmosphere shows that $^1\text{O}_2$ is highly inhibited under N_2 conditions, confirming the presence of $^1\text{O}_2$ during the Fenton oxidation of TCH. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spin trap of 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline *N*-oxide (DMPO- $\cdot\text{OH}$, DMPO- $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$), 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine (TMPO- $^1\text{O}_2$) radical adducts were obtained for Fe-CN/MoO/dark, Fe-CN/MoO/ H_2O_2 /dark, and Fe-CN/MoO/Vis, Fe-CN/MoO/ H_2O_2 /Vis systems (Fig. 8d–f). The spin traps DMPO- $\cdot\text{OH}$ and DMPO- $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ were not detected in Fe-CN/3-MoO/dark, yet both of these spin traps were detected in Fe-CN/3-MoO/ H_2O_2 /dark, suggesting the addition of H_2O_2 contributes to the generation of ROS $\cdot\text{OH}$ and $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$. Besides, a notable increase in the ESR signals of DMPO- $\cdot\text{OH}$, DMPO- $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, and TMPO- $^1\text{O}_2$ spin traps was observed in Fe-CN/MoO/Vis, Fe-CN/3-MoO/ H_2O_2 /Vis compared to Fe-CN/3-MoO/ H_2O_2 /dark, while under visible light irradiation, significantly intense ESR signals were detected for Fe-CN/3-MoO/ H_2O_2 /Vis systems. These results indicate the synergistic effect of H_2O_2 and visible light follows more favorable Fenton oxidation of TCH. Likewise, intense

ESR signals for spin trap TMPO- $^1\text{O}_2$ confirm the existence of singlet oxygen species during the catalytic reaction.

To further explain the activation of H_2O_2 by the atomically dispersed Fe- N_4 sites of the Fe-CN/3-MoO heterojunction structure, the adsorption of H_2O_2 on two different adsorption configurations on Fe- N_4 sites of Fe-CN/MoO interface was calculated by DFT calculation. The adsorption of oxygen of H_2O_2 molecule on the Fe site in Fe-CN/MoO shows no dissociation in their $\cdot\text{OH}$ (configuration I, Fig. 9a). However, configuration II indicates a favorable H_2O_2 molecule dissociation into $\cdot\text{OH}$, where one $\cdot\text{OH}$ adsorbed on the Fe site and the other adsorbed on the C site (Fig. 9b). The H_2O_2 adsorption energy (E_{ads}) on I and II are -2.4 eV and -1.11 eV, respectively (Table S11), suggesting that the H_2O_2 is stable for configuration I and unstable for configuration II, which indicates the favorable adsorption of H_2O_2 on II [21]. This result explains the photo-Fenton reaction of TCH oxidation on the surface of Fe-CN/MoO is more likely, where the one $\cdot\text{OH}$ adsorbed on the Fe sites of the Fe- N_4 and the other on the C site, respectively. Therefore, the experimental results (Fig. 8) combined with DFT calculations (Fig. 9) collectively demonstrate that the oxidation of TC primarily follows Configuration II.

According to the calculated band potentials, the CB and VB potentials of Fe-CN and MoO are -0.81 , 1.89 eV, and 0.58 eV, 3.36 eV, respectively. Considering the conventional heterojunction, if the CB electron of Fe-CN transfers to the CB of MoO, and the VB hole of MoO transfers to the VB of Fe-CN. The CB potential of MoO (0.58 eV) is not sufficiently negative to reduce the surface-adsorbed O_2 molecule to $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ (standard reduction potential of $\text{O}_2/\cdot\text{O}_2^- = -0.33$), and likewise, the VB potential of Fe-CN (1.89 eV) is not sufficiently positive to oxidize the H_2O molecule and generate OH^- , and $\cdot\text{OH}/\text{OH}^- = 1.99$ eV, and $\cdot\text{OH}/\text{OH} = 2.68$ eV). This speculation is inconsistent with the active species trapping and the ESR spin trap results, where it was found that $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, $\cdot\text{OH}$ plays a significant role in the oxidation of TCH. Therefore, as anticipated, at the interface Z-scheme mechanism, the CB electron of MoO will migrate to the VB of Fe-CN and accumulate as the electron trap center, thereby inhibiting the recombination of electron/hole pairs. In this case, the CB potential of Fe-CN (-0.81 eV) is sufficiently negative to reduce the O_2 molecule and generate $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, and the VB of MoO (3.36 eV) is positive enough to oxidize the $\cdot\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Remarkably, the proposed Z-scheme charge transfer in the Fe-CN/MoO/ H_2O_2 /Vis system highly

Fig. 9. Adsorption configuration of H_2O_2 adsorbed on Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction (a) Configuration I, and (b) Configuration II (top and side view, the red, blue, green, golden, and pink colors indicate O, Mo, C, N, and Fe atoms). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

enhances the generation of ROS species and inhibits the recombination of electron/hole pairs via the Z-scheme charge transfer for photostable and longer lifetime oxidation of TCH. Moreover, the atomically dispersed Fe- N_4 active site at the interface Fe-CN/MoO heterojunction serves as the H_2O_2 adsorption site, and the directional concentrated electron density at the Fe- N_4 sites enhances the conversion efficiency of H_2O_2 during the photodegradation reaction.

4. Conclusion

In summary, an interfacial Z-scheme Fe-CN/MoO₃ heterojunction with atomically dispersed Fe- N_4 sites was fabricated with built-in interface iron single sites, offering a powerful platform for enhancing both CO_2 reduction and photo-Fenton reactions. Experimental and density functional theory (DFT) calculations results reveal the regulated local charge density of the Fe atom of the atomically dispersed Fe- N_4 sites and the directional interfacial charge transfer at the Fe-CN and MoO heterojunction interfaces. Moreover, the enhanced interfacial charge dynamic and inhibited electron-hole recombination of photo-generated charge carriers is due to the isolated Fe- N_4 sites acting as the electron trap center during the photocatalytic reaction. This enables the local electron density of Fe directed toward the O atom of MoO₃, which can directionally drive the electron flow towards the central Fe, thus highly enhancing the CO_2 adsorption efficiency and H_2O_2 conversion. The PDOS analysis shows that the d_{yz} and d_z^2 orbitals of the isolated Fe atom of Fe-CN overlap with the p_z orbital of the O atom of MoO₃, which is mainly involved in CO_2 adsorption. This work will inspire future advancements in constructing heterojunctions with other wide band gap semiconductors to optimize the local electron density at central metal active sites for enhancing the catalytic activity.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Muhammad Arif: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ayaz Mahsud:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Data curation. **Haoran Xing:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Abdul Hannan Zahid:** Writing –

review & editing. **Qian Liang:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Muhammad Amjad Majeed:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Amjad Ali:** Writing – original draft, Visualization. **Xiazhang Li:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Zhansheng Lu:** Validation, Software. **Francis Leonard Deepak:** Writing – original draft. **Tahir Muhmood:** Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Yinjuan Chen:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2024.11.038>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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